

CERTAIN STYLES EXPRESSED IN UZBEK ANECDOTES EVENTS

Husaynova Mahliyo Ma'rufjon kizi

The Fergana Branch of Tashkent University of Information Technology

Teacher of the Department of Uzbek Language and Humanities

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Abstract: This article talks about anecdotes, which are one of the bright examples of Uzbek folklore, and linguistic and stylistic phenomena in their production. In addition, several examples of the text of anecdotes are analyzed.

Key words: Uzbek folklore, folklore, anecdote, anecdote, polysemantic game.

The linguistic and stylistic characteristics of anecdotes are the requirements of the times. Research based on this is a huge task for the science of Uzbek linguistics. Tasks are characteristic of all linguistic aspects of our national language; it also allows for deep understanding of linguistic and stylistic features. From this point of view, our nation is huge and priceless. Various linguistic phenomena characteristic of our rich mother tongue, that's it including, although it is small in size, it is very deep in content, society. Uzbek anecdotes covering all aspects of life: extensive research, unlimited expression in their speech to study the possibilities and deeply inculcate these issues in the minds of people. Introduction to the linguostylistic features of the texts today is considered one of the most urgent tasks of the day.

Anecdotes are one of the artistic genres typical of the languages of all nations and their text is a specific linguistic phenomenon in world linguistics as it has been relatively widely researched from a scientific-theoretical point of view, but in Uzbek linguistics, this problem has not been studied in depth yet. It is known that the prevalence of anecdotes in the forms of oral and written artistic speech is also distinguished by. From this point of view, literature theory, in research works on folk oral poetic creativity, some scientific and theoretical on the issue of the influence of anecdotes on the work of writers of anecdotes by Uzbek literary scholars the issue of artistic and aesthetic properties was touched upon 80, but from the point of view of linguistics, there is little to research the text of anecdotes; attention is focused.

Polysemantic play is a way of making puns using words with multiple meanings. Scientist H. Razzokov polysemous, homonymous words actively participate in word games, this subtle quality in words is to "play" words at will, to change the place of words and logical accents in one sentence, emphasizes that by creating inversions, several different meanings can be derived.

Polysemous words are a linguistic tool that helps to expand the expressive possibilities of speech. For example:

Did the girls come?

They came to come.

One of the methods of linguistic games is to play with multiple meanings of the word

is considered, that is, different objects in the reality of one word and from the nature of serving to report events

is used. For example:

One day, when a thief broke the door of a store, a man asked, "What are you doing?"

he asked. The thief said, "Can't you see, I'm ringing the bell?"

It's not coming out", the thief said: "The voice will come out tomorrow".

In this anecdote, the situational ambiguity of the word "voice" is observed

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a sound from a musical instrument and a sensational event, in this case it is expected that there will be noise due to the theft in the store.

Clean my suit.

I cleaned it.

Clean my pants.

I cleaned it.

Clean my shoes.

Do you have a pocket for your shoes? ...

In this anecdote, the polysemantic word "to clean" took part in the creation of a pun. This word caused laughter as it literally means "to whisper". So, the means of creating humor in the text: ambiguous word and presupposition (hidden meaning).

Antonyms are also one of the sources of language games. The phenomenon of antonymy does not occur often in the anecdotes we have analyzed.

The jealous woman said to the ground: "Have you caught your eye on a beautiful girl?"

you forget you have a wife. "You're talking nonsense, wife," said the husband

I remember that I have a wife.

—Antonymic game|| is a word game with opposite meanings. For example, academician - academician (Gafur Ghulam)

As we have observed, the phenomenon of homonymy is synonymy in Uzbek anecdotes more common than the event:

In the geography lesson: - Teshavoy, tell us about the Panama Canal.
- Master, our television does not show such a channel.

In this anecdote, you can see the homonymy of the word "channel" - a play on words canal, a waterway, a navigable waterway, and a television channel based on the difference in the conceptualization of their meanings.

So, as in any language, Uzbek anecdotes give the Uzbek language a national spirit and a unique national color. From this point of view, the study of linguo-stylistics of anecdotes is of great importance in creating a scientific-theoretical basis for solving a number of complex and diverse problems of language, in general, speech culture.

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